

The Offence of Mafia-Type Organised Criminal Group

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ABSTRACT

This work examines the legal framework, doctrinal evolution, and jurisprudential developments surrounding Article 416-bis of the Italian Criminal Code, with particular attention to the constitutive elements of mafia-type associations and their contemporary transformations. It analyses the interpretative models elaborated by courts and scholars, the emergence of ‘relocated’ and ‘new’ mafias, and the scope of aggravating circumstances connected to mafia-related behaviour. The study also explores the complex issue of external participation, highlighting the criteria established by case law for assessing contributory involvement in mafia associations.

1. Introduction of the Article 416 bis of the Italian Criminal Code

The provision of Article 416 bis was introduced into the Italian Penal Code by Act of Parliament No. 646 of September 13, 1982 (“Rognoni-La Torre Act”, from the names of the proponents). The urgency of this introduction was raised by the Report of August 7, 1963, in which the Parliamentary Commission of Inquiry into the mafia phenomenon in Sicily, called for a change in the relevant criminal legislation and preventive measures. This Report led to the enactment of Act No. 575 of May 31, 1965, in which the term “mafia-type association” was used for the first time. However, before the introduction of Article 416 bis, participation in the Mafia was not entirely unpunished, since both legal scholarship and case law had tried to bring cases of Mafia association within the scope of Article 416 of the Criminal Code.

In the Report accompanying Bill no. 1581 (submitted on March 31, 1980, by Representative Pio La Torre and others), regarding the objectives pursued by this amendment, it is stated that:

"This provision aims to fill a legislative gap already highlighted by jurists and legal practitioners, as the provision of Article 416 of the Criminal Code (criminal association) is not sufficient to cover all types of mafia associations, which sometimes do not have a criminal program according to the meaning given to this typical element by Article 416 of the Criminal Code, entrusting the achievement of objectives to the intimidating force of the mafia bond as such: intimidating force which in Sicily and Calabria achieves its effects even without resorting to threats or violence"^[1].

2. The constitutive elements of the crime of mafia-type organization

The provision referred to in Article 416 bis of the Italian Criminal Code, introduced by Article 1 of Act of the Parliament No. 646 of 13 September 1982, provides:

“Anyone who is a member of a mafia-type association of three or more persons shall be punished by imprisonment for a term of ten to fifteen years.

Those who promote, direct or organize the association shall be punished, for this reason, by imprisonment for twelve to eighteen years.

The association is considered as a mafia-type organization when those who are part of it make use of the force of intimidation of the associative bond and of the condition of subjugation and of code of silence that derives from it to commit crimes, to acquire in a direct or indirect way the management or the control of economic activities, administrative concessions, authorizations, public procurement and public services, or to achieve unfair profits or advantages for oneself or others, or in order to prevent or hinder the free exercise of voting or to procure votes for oneself or others during electoral consultations.

[1] Cass. pen., SS.UU., 27 maggio 2021, n. 36958; upon careful ex post observation, Article 416 bis of the Italian Criminal Code appears to be shaped as a two-sided concept, partly focused on the past and partly open to the future. Indeed, while the definition of mafias provided in paragraph 3 of this article is the result of a retrospective observation, aimed at capturing the situation at the time and, therefore, the old mafia groups rooted in specific areas of the peninsula, the referral clause contained in paragraph 8, which establishes the applicability of the crimes in question also to criminal groups, however named and wherever rooted, that borrow the behavioral dynamics and aims of classic associations, denotes a predictive focus on the possible evolution of this type of crime (Giuseppe Amarelli, Gli elementi costitutivi della condotta associativa, *Penale Diritto e Procedura* (2025), <https://www.penaledp.it/gli-elementi-costitutivi-della-condotta-associativa> (last visited Jan. 14, 2026).

If the association is armed, the penalty of imprisonment from twelve to twenty years shall apply in the cases provided for in the first paragraph and from fifteen to twenty-six years in the cases provided for in the second paragraph.

The association is considered armed when the participants have the availability, for the purpose of the association, of weapons or explosive materials, even if concealed or kept in place of storage.

If the economic activities of which the members intend to take or maintain control are financed in whole or in part by the price, product, or profit of crimes, the penalties established in the previous paragraphs shall be increased by one third to one half.

Against the convicted person confiscation of goods that were used or were conceived to commit the crime and of the goods that are its price, product, profit is always mandatory.

The provisions of this article also apply to the Camorra, the 'Ndrangheta and other associations, whatever locally named, including foreign ones, which, using the intimidating force of the associative bond, pursue objectives corresponding to those of mafia-type associations”.

The intimidating force of the association, the condition of subjugation and the code of silence are necessary and essential elements for the crime referred to in Art. 416 bis.

2.1. The power of intimidation

The cornerstone of Article 416 bis is the power of intimidation: not just any attitude of oppression or abuse of power, but a force that, originating from the association, is capable of generating a condition of subjugation and silence.

The intimidating force often identified as “criminal fame” thanks to which the mafia organization projects its activities into the future. Genetically, therefore, the force must be referred to association as such and must characterize the structure itself, becoming an unavoidable quality, capable of imposing itself autonomously^[2].

It is therefore not necessary that the power of intimidation is in actual terms used by each member of the criminal organization, but it is nevertheless required that they are in concrete in a position and aware that they can use them. The association must in fact be able to exert pressure through the bond of membership, in the sense that it is the association and only the association, regardless of the commission of specific acts of intimidation by individual members, that expresses the mafia method and its capacity for oppression, which is the typical tool used by members to achieve the association's objectives.

It is therefore necessary that the association has achieved, in concrete terms, an effective capacity for intimidation in the surrounding environment in which it operates, to the extent that it spreads a permanent aura of widespread fear around itself. The intimidation has to be objectively perceptible and has to remain alive even regardless of individual acts of intimidation carried out by this or that member.

Furthermore, even in the absence of evidence of actual acts of intimidation and violence, the element of intimidating force must be inferred from circumstances that demonstrate the association's capacity to instill fear, linked to a general perception of its efficiency in exercising physical and/or moral coercion^[3].

[2] Cass. pen., sez. VI, 23 giugno 1999, n. 2402.

[3] Cass. pen., sez. F, 12 settembre 2013, n. 44315.

2.2. Subjugation

Although subjugation and the code of silence are difficult to separate in practice, since the former is the natural prerequisite for the latter, both have a certain conceptual autonomy: subjugation refers to the state of submission to the will and power of the group, while code of silence refers to the refusal to cooperate with public authorities, essentially caused by fear of revenge and retaliation.

Such an attitude, which must be sufficiently widespread may stem both from fear of harm and from the performing of threats that could in any case cause significant damage. So that it is objectively clear that cooperation with the judicial authorities will not prevent harmful reprisals against the complainant, given the ramifications of the association, its efficiency, and the existence of other unidentifiable individuals with the power to harm those who dare to oppose them^[4].

Therefore, it is necessary for the mafia association to have achieved an effective and objectively verifiable capacity for intimidation. This means that the dangerous nature of the case implies that the organization must be concretely capable of endangering public and economic order, and freedom of participation in political life, since the mere danger that its constitutive elements may manifest themselves is not sufficient.

The offence of mafia-type association cannot be deemed consummated without an assessment of the concrete harm, which must be concrete and effective, precisely in relation to the use of mafia methods understood in an objective sense. In this sense, the abstract danger does not constitute the crime^[5].

2.3 Code of silence (“omertà”)

As regards the code of silence, this can be seen in a behavior that involves non-cooperation with the authorities, reticence, and even aiding and abetting.

It is important to emphasize that the danger to public order is posed by the very existence of the mafia association, regardless of the aims it pursues. For this reason, the association may also engage in lawful activities. The conditions of subjugation and silence must be inferred from the conduct of unrelated third parties who suffer the unlawful action. However, it has been recognized that subjugation and code of silence could be two ways in which the associative bond is expressed both within and outside the mafia-type association^[6]. With regard to mafia-type associations, the code of silence, which is causally linked to the intimidating power of the criminal group, must be sufficiently widespread, even if not generalized throughout the territory in question, and may derive not only from fear of personal harm, but also from the threat of potentially significant harmful consequences, so that there is a widespread belief that cooperating with the judicial authorities will not prevent retaliation against the complainant due to the ramifications of the organization, to its efficiency, and to the existence of individuals with the power to harm those who dare to oppose it^[7].

[4] Cass. pen., sez. VI, 11 gennaio 2000, n. 1612.

[5] Cass. pen., sez. VI, 2 luglio 2019, n. 9001.

[6] Cass. pen., SS.UU., 27 maggio 2021, n. 36958.

[7] Cass. pen., sez. II, 20 dicembre 2022, n. 11118.

2.4. The participation in a mafia-type association

Unlike the activities of leadership, promotion, and organization, which are punishable under the second paragraph of Article 416 bis, the expression “being part of” has given rise to more interpretative doubts.

Therefore, the participant's conduct may consist of providing a contribution of any kind, not occasional and in any case causally directed at preserving the existence or strengthening the association. This contribution must be supported by awareness of the existence of the criminal association and the willingness to join it, in order to pursue the typical aims of the association through the use of mafia methods, even if the actual achievement of these aims can be ignored.

Therefore, the relevant indicators of punishable participation that constitute elements of the offense are identified as follows: **(i)** entry into the association, even if not accompanied by a particular ritual; **(ii)** recognition of the member by the group and reciprocal acceptance by the other members; **(iii)** adherence to the rules of the association agreement and the consequent assumption of membership status by the new member.

The status of member, in return, generates: **1)** the hierarchical obedience and silence; **2)** the commitment in the form of “making oneself available” to carry out the association's program; **3)** the power to give orders according to a perspective of functionality to the interests of the group.

Therefore, participation in a mafia association cannot be established in the absence of such a reciprocal relationship. Participation cannot only provide advantages—of any kind—on the member, freeing him from any action or obligation.

2.5 The penalties

With regard to penalties, Article 416-bis provides for severe sanctions for participants in mafia associations, modulating responsibility according to the role held within the organization. Promoters, leaders, or organizers^[8] are punished with imprisonment from 12 to 18 years^[9]; mere participants with imprisonment from 10 to 15 years.

If the association is armed^[10], the penalties are increased of one third^[11]. The law considers the organization to be armed when its members own weapons, even if these are not directly used at the time the association is discovered.

If the economic activities over which the associates intend to assume or maintain control are financed in whole or in part with the proceeds, product, or profits of crimes, the sanctions provided for in the previous paragraphs shall be increased by one-third to one-half^[12].

[8] For the purposes of establishing liability pursuant to Article 416-bis, paragraph 2, of the Italian Criminal Code, it is necessary, regardless of the recognition of a generically defined decisive role, that managerial positions and senior roles are actually exercised and that they are recognizable and recognized within the association, as well as, if exercised at the local level, by the hierarchically superior structures (Cass. pen., sez. I, 10 giugno 2021, n. 26268).

According to established case law, the hypotheses provided for in paragraphs 1 and 2 of Article 416-bis of the Criminal Code refer to structurally differentiated criminal organizations of an alternative nature, which have in common only the reference to a mafia-type association, so that the conduct of those who promote, direct, or organize the association constitutes an autonomous offense and not an aggravating circumstance of participation in the association itself (Cass. pen., sez. II, 12 giugno 2014, n. 40254); The activities carried out by those who promote, direct, or organize the association—far from being characterized by the presence of elements that distinguish them from mere participation—express an alternative nature that justifies the different negative value attributed by the Legislature through a distinct sanctioning treatment (Cass. pen., sez. V, 21 febbraio 2014, n. 8430).

[9] See Art. 112, paragraph 1, n. 2 Criminal Code.

[10] The association is considered armed when its members have access to weapons or explosives, even if concealed or kept in storage, for the purpose of achieving the association's objectives (Art. 416 bis, paragraph 5, Criminal Code).

[11] If the association is armed, the penalty of imprisonment from twelve to twenty years shall apply in the cases referred to in the first paragraph and from fifteen to twenty-six years in the cases referred to in the second paragraph (art. 416 bis, paragraph 4, Criminal Code).

[12] Art. 416 bis, paragraph 6, Criminal Code.

In addition, measures are applied to the convicted person^[13], such as permanent disqualification from public office and confiscation^[14] of illegally accumulated assets.

The provisions of Article 416 bis and the penalties provided for also apply to the Camorra, the 'Ndrangheta and other associations, whatever locally named, including foreign ones^[15], which, using the intimidating force of their association, pursue aims corresponding to those of mafia-type associations.

3. Case Law of the Supreme Court of Cassation on Article 416 bis

Over the years, the Supreme Court of Cassation's has made a pivotal contribution to the interpretative development of Article 416-bis of the Italian Criminal Code, delineating the structure, scope, and operational dynamics of mafia-type associations. The Court's role in shaping a coherent jurisprudential framework was capable of addressing the evolving manifestations of organised crime, both within traditional mafia structures and in their contemporary variants. Central to this analysis is the judicial construction of the "mafia method," whose constitutive elements—intimidatory force, subjugation, and the code of silence—serve as markers for distinguishing mafia-type criminality from ordinary forms of association.

The chapter explores how the Court has progressively elaborated criteria for establishing the material and psychological elements of participation, clarifying the meaning of "being part" of a mafia-type organisation. Special attention is devoted to landmark rulings that have refined the distinction between internal membership and external participation, particularly through the elaboration of causal contribution, functional integration, and the notion of being "at the disposal" of the criminal group.

Moreover, the jurisprudence discussed herein highlights the hybrid nature of the offence—combining elements of both danger and damage—while offering interpretative guidelines on the evidentiary thresholds required to infer associative links, ritual affiliation, or contributory conduct. The case law of the Supreme Court's thus provides an in-depth examination of its efforts to reconcile constitutional guarantees with the imperative of combating increasingly sophisticated forms of mafia infiltration into social, political, and economic spheres.

After a period marked by the prominent role played by the Supreme Court of Cassation which culminated in the trilogy of landmark decisions Demitry, Carnevale, and Mannino (issued between

[13] With regard to the replacement or revocation of precautionary measures applied for the offense referred to in Article 416-bis of the Criminal Code, where the conduct is attributable to participation in a "historic" mafia association, characterized by long-standing roots and recognized stability, the judge has a reduced burden of proof regarding the persistence of the precautionary danger, even in cases where there is a significant time gap between the application of the measure and the request for its replacement, given that the current nature of the requirements is inherent in this type of offense and can only be excluded in the presence of evidence of the termination of all relations between the accused and the association (Cass. pen., sez. II, 14 dicembre 2022, n. 12197).

[14] See Cass. pen., sez. VI, 16 febbraio 2021, n. 21741, in which "For the purposes of confiscation pursuant to Article 416-bis, paragraph seven, of the Italian Criminal Code of an entire company's assets, it is necessary that the company be classified as mafia-related, i.e., that there be a specific and concrete correlation between the management and activities of the company and the activities attributable to the association, since the mere participation of the administrator in the criminal association is insufficient in itself".

[15] With reference to foreign criminal organizations, for the purposes of classification pursuant to Article 416-bis of the Criminal Code, it is not sufficient to reconstruct links with the so-called parent organization (in this case, the Nigerian organization "Black Axe"), as the criteria of the so-called historical mafias cannot be applied to such associations. Instead, in line with the requirements for new mafias, it is necessary to ascertain whether the association: a) has achieved criminal fame and prestige, independent and distinct from that of its individual members, such that it is capable of maintaining them even if the latter are rendered harmless; b) has actually demonstrated a capacity for intimidation, although not necessarily through acts of violence or threats; c) has demonstrated a capacity for intimidation that is effectively perceived as such and has consequently produced a code of silence in the "territory" in which the association is active (Cass. pen., sez. VI, 21 febbraio 2023, n. 14444).

1994 and 2005), the Modaffari judgment signalled the renewed intervention of the Joint Divisions within the jurisprudential discourse aimed at clarifying the conceptual contours and operational scope of the offence of mafia-type association.

3.1. Methods and purposes

Although the novelty introduced by Article 416 bis focuses on the method used by members, the most direct threat concerns public order from two points of view: the “objective” one, understood as the set of conditions that guarantee public safety and tranquility, and the “subjective” one, meant as the moral freedom of the population to make decisions and choices freely, without coercion from any organization established for the purpose of breaking the law and profiting from it.

Nevertheless, other equally significant threats posed by mafia-type association concern the moral freedom of citizens, the democratic order, the freedom of the market and economic initiative, as well as the impartiality and the proper functioning of public administration.

Although the existence of a hierarchy of roles is considered decisive for the identification of a mafia-type association, as well as the existence of a specific organizational and logistical structure, the territorial scope of operations or the type of crimes committed, the typical nature of the association model outlined in Article 416 bis of the Criminal Code lies in the ways in which the association manifests itself and not in the purposes it intends to pursue.

Moreover, the coexistence of lawful and unlawful purposes ultimately attributes to the ‘method’ the role of a key element of the criminal offense, a watershed aimed at circumscribing the criminally relevant notion of ‘mafia-type association’.

In particular, with regard to the method, an association is defined as mafia-like when its members “use the intimidating power of the association and the resulting subjugation and code of silence.” As regards its aims, these range from the implementation of an intrinsically illegal program (such as the commission of crimes or the obtaining of unjust profits and advantages, or even the influencing of voting freedom), to the pursuit of objectives that are lawful in themselves, such as “directly or indirectly acquiring the management or control of economic activities, concessions, authorizations, contracts, and public services” or “procuring votes for oneself or others in elections.”

Compared to simple criminal association^[16], in mafia-type association (Art. 416 bis) there is a reversal of the relationship between means and goals. In fact, while for the common associate the commission of crimes is the purpose of the organized criminal group, for the mafia associate, criminal activity is the mean to pursue a more ambitious goal, consisting in the stable control of a part of social life in order to guarantee parasitic enrichment.

This implies the possibility that some individuals join the mafia association not directly with a view to carrying out criminal activities, but only to participate in the division of profits (as is often the case with entrepreneurs in collusion) or to achieve lasting territorial supremacy over all kinds of activities, offering a stable contribution to the association's survival and obtaining various advantages in return. Hence the mafia's ability to increasingly expand its membership is different from common associations which are usually made up of a limited number of members.

[16] Art. 416 Criminal Code.

Under Article 416 bis, a combined examination of the association's methods and objectives leads to the configuration of a "mixed" or "complex" offence, which is structurally unique and whose establishment requires the presence of a *quid pluris* beyond the mere multi-person structure and its criminal programme.

In this regard, legal scholarship and jurisprudence have questioned the actual nature of the crime: crime of damage ("reato di danno") or crime of danger ("reato di pericolo").

1. **An initial interpretative approach** characterized the offence as one of the abstract endangerment, considering Article 416 bis to constitute a special provision in relation to Article 416, in which the distinctive element is the so-called mafia method (intimidation), whose existence may be merely posited and intended in conceptual terms, without requiring its explicit or overt manifestation^[17].
2. **A second approach**, on the other hand, believes that the damage component manifests itself with regard to the public order and moral freedom, while the danger component is only relevant with regard to the economic order, the proper functioning and the impartiality of public administration. The damage is identified precisely in the use of mafia methods, which must be considered objectively, i.e. it must be recognizable from the outside and concretely verifiable^[18].
3. **A third line of interpretation**, recognizes the mixed nature of the offense in question, in the sense that it simultaneously assumes the nature of danger, in that it is directed toward the commission of an indeterminate series of crimes, and, on the other hand, assumes the nature of damage, in relation to the exploitation of its intimidating capacity^[19].

3.2. The meaning of the participation

Having reconstructed the structure and legal nature of the mafia-type association as a *hybrid endangerment offence* ("mixed nature"), the Joint Divisions of the Court of Cassation in the Modaffari judgment^[20] turns to the notion of *criminally relevant membership* (participation). In this respect, the Court surveys the main interpretative approaches.

1. **The purely psychological conception:** liability under Article 416-bis of the Criminal Code would rest on an inner mental attitude of adherence to the criminal fellowship. This view is, however, empirically elusive and poorly compatible with the principles of personal culpability, materiality of the offence, and harm/offensiveness;
2. **The causal model** (the *Arslan* judgment^[21]): falling within paragraph 1 of Article 416-bis is any minimal yet not insignificant contribution made by the individual to the life of the association and in furtherance of its aims. While more consonant with constitutional criminal-law principles, this model does not fully capture the distinctive tenor of mafia "membership," encapsulated in the statutory expression "to be part of";
3. **The organisational model** (the *Demitry* judgment^[22]): it emphasises the relational integration of the participant within the associative structure, highlighting indicia such as entry into the

[17] See Cass. pen., sez. II, 15 maggio 2015, n. 25360; Cass. pen., sez. V, 26 giugno 2003, n. 38412.

[18] Cass. pen., sez. VI, 3 giugno 1993, n. 1793.

[19] Cass. pen., SS.UU., 27 maggio 2021, n. 36958.

[20] *Ibidem*.

[21] Cass. pen., sez. I, 24 aprile 1985, n. 170230.

[22] Cass. pen., sez. I, 5 ottobre 1994, n. 16.

fellowship, recognition by the group, the bond of obedience, *affectio societatis* (the intention to be part of the criminal organization), and the powers deriving from affiliation.

4. **The syncretic-additive model** (the *Mannino* judgment^[23]): it stresses the functional nature of one's insertion into the association, requiring at trial not only the formal status of member but also proof of the dynamic dimension of that role through acts of associative militancy expressive of the function thereby assumed.

In *Mannino* judgment, the Supreme Court thus distinguishes between a **substantive profile** (the constitutive elements of the offence under paragraph 1 of Article 416-bis) and a **procedural-evidentiary profile** (the proof of the criminally relevant conduct and its symptomatic indicia). According to the Court, that bifurcation—and the ensuing uncertainty as to whether some *Mannino* indicia count as elements of the offence or merely as evidence—has underpinned divergent lines of authority concerning the probative value of ritual affiliation.

Among the various interpretative approaches reviewed, the Court—ultimately, in the *Modaffari* judgment—reaffirms its adherence to the so-called *mixed conception* formulated in 2005 with the *Mannino* decision, holding that:

“The conduct constituting participation in a mafia-type association consists in the stable integration of the individual into the organisational structure of the association. Such integration must, in the specific circumstances of the case, be shown to establish a condition of being ‘**at the disposal**’ of the criminal group for the pursuit of its common unlawful objectives. In compliance with the principles of materiality and offensiveness of criminal conduct, ritual affiliation may constitute a serious indication of participation in the criminal organisation where—on the basis of reliable and consolidated maxims of experience, and in light of contextual elements demonstrating its seriousness and authenticity—it represents not merely an expression of intent, but rather a mutually binding pact giving rise to a permanent contribution between the affiliate and the association.”

3.3. The external participation (aiding and abetting)

The Joint Sections of the Court of Cassation^[24] have upheld the legal principle that external complicity can also be established for the crime of mafia-type association referred to in Article 416 bis^[25].

In distinguishing between the categories of internal participation and external involvement, a “participant” is defined as someone who, being permanently and organically integrated into the organization of the mafia association, is “part” of that organization. This expression must not be construed in a static sense—as the mere acquisition of a formal status—but rather in a dynamic sense, referring to the *effective role* concretely performed by the individual and to the *tasks functionally required* of him within the organisation. In order for the criminal association to attain its objectives, the subject must maintain a condition of operational availability for activities organised by the group.

In terms of evidence of participation, all factual indicators are relevant, from which the core of participation can be logically deduced, i.e. the stable interpenetration of the subject in the organization of the association. There must be serious and precise indications (including the initiation ritual, the title

[23] Cass., SS.UU., 12 luglio 2005, n. 33748.

[24] *Ibidem*.

[25] Cass. pen., sez. I, 5 ottobre 1994, n. 16; Cass. pen. SS.UU., 12 luglio 2005, n. 33748; Cass. pen. SS.UU., 30 ottobre 2002, n. 22327;

of “man of honor,” and the commission of crimes for specific purposes), from which it can be deduced with certainty that the bond is permanent and that the person is permanently “at the disposal” of the criminal association for all its activities.

Instead, the role of “external” participant is assumed by the person who, not being permanently part of the organizational structure of the mafia association and lacking therefore the *affectio societatis* (not being part of it), nevertheless the person provides a concrete, specific, conscious and voluntary contribution. This contribution must have an actual causal relevance for the purposes of preserving or strengthening the operational capabilities of the association and it is in any case directed towards the realization, even partial, of the criminal program of the same.

Therefore, the structural requirements that characterize the significant core of external participation by individuals are:

1. all the constitutive elements of the crime in question are present, whether attempted or committed, and the conduct of participation is objectively or subjectively linked to these elements.
2. the contribution of the external participant, whether material or moral, is different but working in synergy with that of the internal participants. That type of contribution should be a necessary condition for the commission of the criminal act carried out by the whole criminal organization and a condition for the causation of the damage to the protected legal interest, such as the integrity of public order.

As regards the **psychological element** of the external participant, intent must involve both the essential elements of the offense and the causal contribution made by his behavior to the actual commission of the act.

It is therefore required that the external participant must be fully aware that his support is beneficial to the preservation or strengthening of the association: he ‘*knows*’ and ‘*wants*’ his contribution to be directed towards the realization, even partial, of the criminal program of the association.

With regard to the examination of the **causal link**, this is a causal assessment aimed at defining criminally relevant conduct and therefore at defining the scope of the offense. The *Mannino* judgment^[26] holds that it is not sufficient for the contribution provided by the external participant to be merely capable, in abstract terms, of increasing the risk that the crime be committed. This is because such contribution may prove, *ex post*, to be irrelevant—or even counterproductive—from a factual standpoint with respect to the occurrence of the harmful event.”

Calogero Mannino is charged with the crime of aiding and abetting a mafia association “for having - by exploiting his personal and political power and the relationships deriving from his position as a prominent member of the Sicilian Christian Democracy Party - systematically and knowingly contributed to the activities and achievement of the criminal aims of Cosa Nostra”.

The Joint Sections of the Supreme Court, called upon to answer in the *Mannino* case the question of whether external involvement in the crime of mafia-type association can be established, (more precisely, in the context of an agreement between the criminal association and an electoral candidate whereby the association provides electoral support in exchange for commitments of political favour), unanimously agree with the previous case law of the Court of Cassation about

[26] Cass., SS.UU., 12 luglio 2005, n. 33748.

this matter^[27].

Once the hypothesis of charges relating to the political-mafia electoral pact has been put forward, it is therefore necessary to search for and acquire evidence of concrete factual elements from which it can be inferred *a posteriori* that the pact produced positive results in terms of the actual strengthening or consolidation of the mafia association.

With regard to the interpretative question referred to in the introduction and submitted for examination by these Joint Sections, the following principle must therefore be stated, in accordance with Article 173, paragraph 3 of the implementing provisions of the Code of Criminal Procedure:

“External involvement in the crime of mafia-type association can be configured in the case of political-mafia electoral exchange, whereby the politician, in exchange for support in the electoral competition, undertakes to act in favor of the criminal association once elected, even without being a member of it, provided that: a) the commitments made by the politician are serious and concrete; b) the commitments made by the politician have had a real and significant impact on maintaining or strengthening the operations of the criminal organization or its branches”.

Another important judgment on the subject of external involvement is Cass. pen., sez. V, 13 ottobre 2015, n. 2653 on the appeal lodged by Paron Angelo Ermete against the judgment of Court of Appeal of Venice, 23 ottobre 2014, n. 1220.

With this judgment, the Venice Court of Appeal reaffirmed Paron's liability with regard to the crime of external involvement.

Paron was a Carabinieri Marshal serving in the Special Operations Unit (ROS) in Padua, who was indicted and tried in proceedings arising from a wide-ranging investigation into the so-called Brenta Mafia^[28].

According to the judgment of appeal, Marshal Paron allegedly provided information covered by official secrecy, giving rise to specific unlawful acts carried out by the aforementioned mafia.

With regard to these criminal acts, the Court of Appeal held, on the one hand, that Marshal Paron had maintained contact exclusively with the leaders of the organisation, to whom he provided information protected by official secrecy and functionally instrumental to the survival and operational capability of the criminal association.

On the other hand, the Court simultaneously asserted that the association as a whole derived increased security and boldness in its criminal initiatives from the awareness that the group benefitted from the “protection” afforded by the non-commissioned officer.

According to the appellate judgment, such awareness—extended to all members of the criminal organisation—allegedly encouraged them to undertake increasingly audacious unlawful activities, confident that they could rely upon the covert support of the Marshal.

This appeal lodged with the Supreme Court of Cassation was deemed unfounded and was rejected.

The appeal does not question the fact that Marshal Paron was regularly paid a “monthly salary” of 5 million lire (a considerable sum in the 1990s). However, the appeal argues that this is not sufficient to consider Paron an external participant in the Brenta mafia.

[27] Sez. I, 8.6.1992, Battaglini; Sez. V, 16.3.2000, Frasca; Sez. VI, 15.5.2000, Pangallo; Sez. V, 26.5.2001, Allegro; Sez. I, 17.4.2002, Frasca; Sez. V, 13.11.2002, Gorgone; Sez. I, 25.11.2003, Cito; Sez. I, 4.2.2005, Micari.

[28] See Corte d'Assise d'Appello di Venezia n. 3/1994 which stated “the existence of a criminal group that endangered public order and safety in the aforementioned area, committing all sorts of acts of violence and oppression” (p. 40) against citizens and business owners without fear of being reported to the public authorities”.

Therefore judges^[29] consider unnecessary to recall that the *Mannino* ruling^[30] clarified that anyone who, not being permanently part of the organizational structure of the association (lacking of *affection societatis*), provides it with a voluntary, concrete, conscious, and specific contribution, or a contribution causally linked to the preservation or strengthening of the criminal association's (*societas sceleris*) operational capabilities, must be considered an external accomplice.

Furthermore, this causal relationship cannot be assessed solely *ex ante* (in terms of the mere probability of damage to the protected legal interest), but must also be assessed *ex post*, meaning that this relationship must be verified, so to speak, “in the field.”

In this case, the requirements of *ex ante* and *ex post* verification of the causal relationship can therefore be considered positively integrated and satisfied on the basis of historically established facts. In particular, it must be emphasised that the decisive element is the continuity of the relationship—an arrangement that was undoubtedly burdensome for the criminal organisation—which, in order to be maintained over time, must necessarily have yielded an equally enduring advantage in “remunerating” Paron; otherwise, at a certain point, the non-commissioned officer would have been, so to speak, “dismissed” and removed from the organisation’s illicit “payroll.” Moreover, on a historical and factual basis, it emerges that Paron once alerted the leaders of the association that his fellow officers had set a trap for certain affiliates who were preparing to rob a supermarket’s security-cash van.

As regards the **psychological element**, the judgment in question recalls that the *Mannino* judgment clarified that, for the purposes of establishing external participation in a criminal association, the external participant is not required to have the specific intent of the participant (awareness of being part of the association and the desire to keep it alive), but rather *generic intent*, consisting of the awareness and desire to contribute to the achievement of the association's goals.

In conclusion, the ruling in question establishes that a Carabinieri Marshal could not have been unaware that he was working not only in his own interests but also in those of the aforementioned organization, since—in exchange for confidential information—he received a regular “fixed salary” from a mafia-like organization.

4. The offence of mafia-type association: comparative analysis of “traditional mafias” and “relocated criminal structures”

The Italian Legislature did not confine itself to surveying long-standing criminal organisations—such as *Cosa Nostra*, the *'Ndrangheta*, the *Camorra*, and the *Sacra Corona Unita*—all of which possess territorially evocative names, consolidated internal structures, peripheral branches, and a form of criminal “prestige” or notoriety capable of exerting coercive influence over their members. Instead, the Legislature deliberately extended the scope of Article 416-bis of the Italian Criminal Code to encompass an indeterminate range of other groups—including foreign criminal organisations—that, although lacking a historical name or tradition, employ methods and pursue objectives consistent with those of already recognised mafia-type associations.

[29] Cass. pen., sez. V, 13 ottobre 2015, n. 2653.

[30] Cass., SS.UU., 12 luglio 2005, n. 33748.

However, when evaluating the aims pursued by the Legislature, it becomes evident that the features characterising the various criminal groups remain markedly heterogeneous. Mafia-type associations may pursue a wide range of objectives: from the execution of a criminal plan (common to all forms of criminal conspiracy), to the performance of activities that are lawful *per se*—such as directly or indirectly acquiring the management or control of economic undertakings, public concessions, authorisations, contracts, public services, or public procurements; securing unfair profits or advantages; or obstructing the free exercise of voting rights or procuring votes for themselves or others during electoral processes.

This produces a mosaic of purposes so broad that it is difficult to reconcile with the search for any specialised definitional element capable of crystallising the concept of a “mafia-type” organisation.

Nevertheless, the essential core of the offence is enshrined in the third paragraph of Article 416-bis, where the *method* and *purpose* of the mafia-type association are delineated. These purposes must be pursued through a specific method, which facilitates their achievement, thereby establishing a form of association that is structurally distinctive and—above all—marked by an expansive scope of application. The provision is thus designed to repress any associative phenomenon manifesting those characteristic elements of method and purpose.

For this reason, associations lacking a historically recognised criminal identity must be examined in their concrete operational form. In undertaking this interpretative exercise, particular attention must be paid to the specificities of each criminal context, since Article 416-bis inherently requires a normative connection between such contemporary phenomena and the “historical” mafias. This, in turn, demands a careful interpretative assessment to identify “symmetries” among factual, social, and human realities that may differ substantially from one another^[31].

A distinct analysis is warranted in the case of the so-called locale di *'Ndrangheta*, where the relationship between the territorial articulation and the “parent organisation” acquires particular significance. Due to the adoption of an organisational structure that reproduces the distinctive features of the parent association—features that constitute its intrinsic essence and reveal its inherent threat to public order—the courts have held that the offence under Article 416-bis is consummated even in the absence of specific criminal acts or overt manifestations of intimidatory force.

With regard to a branch of a Calabrian *'Ndrangheta* clan operating in a Swiss municipality, the Supreme Court has recognised that modern communication technologies have propagated knowledge of the typical *'Ndrangheta* method even within geographical areas once considered resistant or immune to mafia infiltration. In such cases, proof of concrete intimidation, submission, or *omertà* (code of silence) within the local population is not required; the oppressive effect on the surrounding environment is presumed by virtue of the reputation and criminal prestige accumulated by the parent

[31] With reference to a locale of *'Ndrangheta* in Lombardia Region, see Cass. pen., sez. II, 30 aprile 2015, n. 34147, in which « In the event of a branch of an association referred to in Article 416 bis of the Criminal Code being established outside its territory of origin, it is necessary that the structure of the association is capable of exerting, by its mere existence, a real, effective, and objectively verifiable capacity for intimidation, capable of bending the will of those who come into contact with its members to its own ends ...»; About a locale of *'Ndrangheta* in Piedmont Region «The associative model outlined in Article 416 bis of the Criminal Code lies precisely in the “mafia method” (intimidating force of the associative bond, subjugation, and code of silence), rather than in the aims, so that, in the absence of evidence of specific acts of violence, the intimidating force of the mafia can be inferred from: a) the association's current ability to instill fear; b) general collective perception of the criminal group's efficiency in exercising physical coercion such as to achieve the silent submission of members to the organization ...» (Cass. pen., sez. V, 20 dicembre 2013, n. 14582); As far as a locale in Veneto Region is concerned, the indicators revealing the existence and operation of the mafia-type organization in question (*'Ndrangheta* in the province of Verona) can be inferred from a number of factors: a) parasitic exploitation of the criminal reputation of the original *'Ndrangheta* clans; b) use of mafia methods. This mafia method was achieved by leveraging the interests of Venetian entrepreneurs (especially in the construction sector) to acquire large sums of cash from the clans, both in order to restructure companies without resorting to bank loans and, more often, to illegally reduce the tax base with consequent tax advantages (Corte d'Appello di Venezia, 4.7.2024).

organisation over time^[32].

The now widespread notion of the 'Ndrangheta *locale* therefore transcends the idea of a mere “relocation” of the parent group. Rather, it represents a criminal reality which, while maintaining a strong bond with the original association, simultaneously exhibits structural, functional, and operational autonomy—an autonomy that ensures its own continuity while externally demonstrating the organisation’s capacity for expansion^[33].

This phenomenon is not unfamiliar to judicial precedent. The courts have repeatedly examined the so-called “cellular” structure of subversive terrorist organisations, where the classification of the subsidiary cell under Article 270-bis^[34] of the Criminal Code depends primarily on its instrumental relationship to achieving the criminal objectives of the parent structure—even when such a connection is maintained through a “dematerialised” relationship^[35].

5. Article 416-bis and the emergence of “New Mafias”: the externalisation of the intimidatory method

As introduced by the Rognoni–La Torre Act^[36], Article 416-bis of the Italian Criminal Code represents a fundamental instrument for the criminal repression of the most serious forms of organised crime. Although originally conceived to combat the traditional mafias (*Cosa Nostra*, *'Ndrangheta*, and *Camorra*) within their historical territories, case law has progressively extended its reach to encompass non-native, “relocated”, foreign, and so-called “small” mafia-type organisations. These also include more covert forms of exploitation of the mafia method, particularly relating to infiltration into public administration and the conduct of ostensibly lawful—primarily economic—activities^[37].

The so-called “new mafias” constitute criminal associations that do not necessarily exhibit the traditional socio-psychological characteristics that inspired the Legislature in formulating Article 416-bis^[38]. Although the offence is drafted as an open-ended provision designed to encapsulate a complex sociological reality in legal terms, it nonetheless relies upon certain essential indicators, legislatively codified as structural elements of the crime. Over time, however, these indicators have progressively diminished in intensity and practical relevance, leading to the recognition of mafia-type models in which the classic statutory requirements appear attenuated. These developments pertain to

[32] See Cass. pen., sez. V, 11 luglio 2018, n. 47535 concerning a locale of 'Ndrangheta in Switzerland. The evidence emerged in this judgment is: a) links with the Calabrian “parent organization”; b) the composition of the locale, consisting exclusively of individuals of Calabrian origin; c) an organizational structure based on a very precise division of roles; internal positions corresponding to those traditionally found in the 'Ndrangheta; d) strict observance of rituals typical of the “parent organization”.

[33] See Cass. pen., sez. II, 16 dicembre 2022, n. 47538.

[34] Any person who promotes, constitutes, organizes, directs or finances associations which propose to carry out acts of violence with the aim of terrorism or subversion of the democratic order shall be punished by imprisonment for a term of seven to fifteen years. Anyone who participates in such associations shall be punished by imprisonment for a term of five to ten years. For the purposes of criminal law, the purpose of terrorism also occurs when acts of violence are directed against a foreign State, an international institution or body. Against the convicted person, confiscation of goods that were used or were conceived to commit the crime and of the goods that are its price, product, profit is always mandatory.

[35] Giulia Faillaci, Il delitto di associazione di stampo mafioso: tra mafie “storiche” e “delocalizzate”, *Njus*, (2023), Il delitto di associazione di stampo mafioso: tra mafie «storiche» e «delocalizzate» | *Njus.it* (last visited Feb. 1, 2026).

[36] Law No. 646, 13 September 1982.

[37] Francesco Siracusano, La continuità alla mafia tra paradigmi sociologici e rilevanza penale, *Archivio Penale*, (2016), <https://archiviopenale.it/la-contiguita-alla-mafia-tra-paradigmi-sociologici-e-rilevanza-penale/articoli/2019> (last visited Jan. 14, 2026).

[38] «Associations that do not have a historically qualified criminal characteristics must be analyzed in their concrete attitude», Cass. Pen., sez. II, n. 10255/2020, on the subject of “local mafias”, with regard to the Ostia clan.

the phenomenon of “new and small mafias”, which operate alongside but remain distinct from the historical organisations, while diverging from the original paradigms contemplated by the provision^[39].

The central legal question concerns whether the scope of Article 416-bis may be further expanded. Specifically, the mafia method—defined by the exercise of intimidatory force, the imposition of subjugation, and the maintenance of silence—must be reconsidered in light of new associative dynamics. An interdisciplinary approach is therefore required to assess the degree of awareness and specificity inherent in the statutory case, also in light of supranational jurisprudence^[40].

Within this analytical framework, and particularly with respect to mafia infiltration in economic systems, the Court of Cassation has affirmed that the intimidating message may present itself in various forms, each dependent upon the level of “criminal reputation” achieved by the association^[41].

A first form arises where an explicit and targeted mafia-type warning is issued: intimidation, already present within the environment, is reinforced by a direct threat. This may occur when affiliates invoke the name of the organisation to which they belong, using threats or violence to compel the victim to transfer money or other benefits, sometimes explicitly referencing the detention of other associates.

A second form consists of a veiled, indirect warning that, although lacking express verbalisation, clearly signals the association’s interest in prompting an active or passive response from the recipient. For instance, affiliates may request money ostensibly to support detainees, subtly indicating the organisation’s involvement. The victim’s compliance in such cases stems from their awareness of the applicants’ mafia affiliation and of the organisation’s criminal authority^[42].

A **third form** is characterised by the absence of any explicit message, accompanied by an implicit request—silent yet understood—aimed at securing active or passive conduct. This scenario is possible only where the association has attained a level of intimidating power so widespread that any explicit warning becomes unnecessary. The victim may “spontaneously” deliver money to inmates after a simple visit by an affiliate of the organisation.

Concerning the requirement of externalisation of the mafia method, case law has developed three principal orientations.

The **first** maintains that the mafia method must manifest itself externally through positive acts. On this view, the term “use” in Article 416-bis implies that intimidation must take the form of concrete conduct attributable to one or more members of the association^[43].

The **second** approach holds that it is sufficient for the organisation to possess a merely potential capacity to exert intimidation. According to this understanding, the offence may be established even where the association’s intimidating force—deriving from the associative bond—remains latent rather than being exercised in a concrete manner.

The **third**, an intermediate position, identifies both a static and a dynamic dimension of intimidation: in its static aspect, the intimidation must be current, effective, and objectively recognisable; in its dynamic aspect, it may remain potential, provided that it retains the capability of being used to further

[39] Giuliano Turone, *Il delitto di associazione mafiosa*, Milano (2015).

[40] European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), 21.10.2013, rec. no. 42750/09, *Del Rio Prada c. Spain*, paras. 77-79, with extensive references to earlier ECHR case law. In the sense that “offences and penalties must be clearly indicated by law” art. 7 ECHR see most recently European Court of Human Rights, sect. IV, 15.7.2014, rec. no. 45554/08, *Ashlarba c. Georgia*.

[41] Roberto Maria Sparagna, *Metodo mafioso e c.d. mafia silente nei più recenti approdi giurisprudenziali*, *Diritto Penale Contemporaneo*, https://archiviopdc.dirittopenaleuomo.org/upload/1447071200SPARAGNA_2015a.pdf (last visited, Jan. 14, 2026).

[42] A concrete example of this type of manifestation can be found, for example, in Cass. Pen., sez. V, n. 21562/2015.

[43] In legal scholarship, Antonio Balsamo-Sandra Recchione, *Mafie al nord. L’interpretazione dell’art. 416 bis c.p. e l’efficacia degli strumenti di contrasto*, *Diritto Penale Contemporaneo* (2013) <https://archiviopdc.dirittopenaleuomo.org/upload/1381757435BALSAMO-RECCHIONE%202013a.pdf> (last visited, Jan. 14, 2026).

the aims of the association.

In light of these considerations, case law adopts a differentiated approach to the applicability of Article 416-bis.

Where the criminal organisation constitutes an **autonomous and original structure**, the prosecution must demonstrate the existence of all constituent elements of the mafia-type offence, including proof that the relocated organisation has established itself within the surrounding environment in such a way as to generate conditions of subjugation and silence^[44]. If these conditions are not present, the conduct may fall under the general provision of Article 416 concerning simple criminal association.

Conversely, where the organisation functions as a **mere articulation of a traditional mafia association**, maintaining a relationship of dependence or functional connection with the parent organisation, it suffices to establish the existence of such a link in order to engage Article 416-bis^[45].

Recent case law has clarified that the commission of violent or threatening acts—whether completed or attempted—is not always necessary^[46]. The Legislature's original intent in 1982 was to criminalise phenomena whose effects extend beyond explicit threats or acts of violence. Accordingly, the Court of Cassation has held that intimidatory force may be inferred from objective circumstances demonstrating the association's present capacity to instil fear, or from the general perception within the community of the organisation's ability to exercise coercion^[47].

Article 416-bis thus emerges as a **dynamic provision**^[48], capable of adapting to new forms of organised crime and accommodating evolving patterns of mafia-type association^[49].

6. Aggravating circumstances for crimes related to mafia-type activities (art. 416-bis 1 Criminal Code)

Article 416-bis 1 of the Italian Criminal Code (introduced by Legislative Decree No. 21 of 2018 and subsequently amended by Bill No. 60 of 2023) takes into account aggravating and mitigating circumstances for crimes related to mafia activities.

These are circumstances having a so-called **special effect**: their application determines a variation (increase or decrease) in the penalty from one third to one half.

6.1. Aggravating circumstances

Pursuant to paragraph 1, in relation to crimes punishable by a penalty other than life imprisonment, there are two aggravating circumstances: the **use of mafia method and aiding and abetting of mafia-type activities**.

[44] Cass. pen., sez. V, 3 marzo 2015, n. 31666; Cass. pen., sez. V, 22 aprile 2020, n. 12737.

[45] Ibidem.

[46] Cass pen., sez. VI, 22 ottobre 2019, n. 18125; Cass. pen. sez. VI, 13 giugno 2017, n. 41722.

[47] Cass pen., sez. VI, 22 ottobre 2019, n. 18125.

[48] Ibidem.

[49] Edoardo Cipani, l'art. 416-bis c.p. alla luce della recente pronuncia di Cassazione nel processo cd. "mafia capitale": una "fattispecie in movimento" nel rispetto del principio di tassatività e determinatezza, *Giurisprudenza Penale Web*, (2020), https://www.giurisprudenzapenale.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Cipani_gp_2020_6.pdf (last visited, Jan 14, 2026).

The aggravating circumstance of using the mafia method is an objective circumstance in that it concerns the manner of conduct^[50]. It occurs when the person makes use of the intimidating force of the association and the resulting condition of subjugation and code of silence.

According to case law, for the purposes of this aggravating circumstance, it is sufficient for the person to adopt a typically mafia-like conduct. Therefore, this aggravating circumstance does not necessarily presuppose the existence of a mafia-type association^[51].

According to the Court of Cassation, the aggravating circumstance in question is applicable both to members of the association and to those who do not belong to any criminal association.

On the other hand, the aggravating circumstance of aiding and abetting the mafia is characterized by specific intent: the “direct” objective of the criminal conduct shall be the aim of facilitating the activities of the mafia-type association with the crime committed.

In particular, the Court of Cassation stated that this circumstance is subjective, as it relates to the motive for committing the crime^[52].

In other words, what matters is not the actual and real existence of an association attributable to those with the scope of Article 416-bis of the Criminal Code, or that the offender (or even his accomplices) actually belong to it, but the fact of performing the methods similar to those used in criminal organizations. These methods should be characterized precisely by the intimidating force emanating from the victims' awareness that the criminal conduct to which they are subjected is not attributable exclusively to the perpetrator of the conduct they are suffering at that moment, but that the perpetrator can count on the support of third parties who are able to back up his actions, avenge him if necessary, or intervene to help him, even using violent methods; This has the effect of reducing the victim's capacity for ‘resistance’, thus inducing them to comply ‘spontaneously’ and not to react to the unlawful demands.

As clarified by the Supreme Court of Cassation^[53], it is sufficient that the existence of a criminal association appears in the background, because it is evoked by the agent, thus inducing the victim to comply with the aggressor's will - or to abandon any attempt at defense - for fear of more serious consequences. The aim is not only to punish more severely those who commit crimes using mafia methods or with the aim of facilitating mafia associations, but to combat more decisively the attitude of those who, whether or not they are involved in organized crime, behave like “*mafiosi*”. This could also take place through displaying a provocative conduct by exerting on victims that particular coercion or consequent intimidation typical of these criminal associations.

According to case law, circumstance of mafia facilitation presupposes the existence of the association that the agent wishes to facilitate (in contrast with the aggravating circumstance of the

[50] The aggravating circumstance of the mafia method referred to in Article 7 of Decree Law No. 152 of May 13, 1991, converted with amendments into Act no. 203 of July 12, 1991 (now Article 416-bis.1, first paragraph, of the Criminal Code), as it refers to the way in which the criminal act was carried out, is objective at the factual level and can be assessed against the participants, provided that they were aware of the use of the mafia method or ignored it through negligence or error caused by negligence (Cass. pen., sez. IV, 2 febbraio 2022, n. 5136).

[51] Cass. pen., sez. II, 21 settembre 2021, n. 36818; see also Cass. pen., sez. V, 13 giugno 2017, n. 41772; Cass. pen. Sez. V, 8 febbraio 2018, n. 21530 in which it is explained that in order for the aggravating circumstance of the use of “mafia methods” to apply, as provided for in Article 7 of Decree Law No. 152 of May 13, 1991, it is not necessary to prove or contest the existence of a criminal association, as it is sufficient that the violence or threat takes on a “typically” mafia-like form. The aggravating circumstance of the so-called mafia method can therefore also be applied to individuals who are not members of a mafia-type association but who, in committing the act of which they are accused, engage in threatening behavior.

[52] Cass. pen., sez. I, 22 giugno 2022, n. 38770, in which “The aggravating circumstance of the use of “mafia methods,” as referred to in Article 416-bis.1 of the Criminal Code, may be applied in cases where the way in which the conduct is carried out evokes, in concrete terms, in the minds of associates, the intimidating force typical of mafia action, even if the latter is not directly addressed to the passive subjects, but is nevertheless functional to a more facile and secure consummation of the crime.

[53] Cass. pen., sez. II, 21 settembre 2021, n. 36818; see also Cass. pen., sez. VI, 19 febbraio 1998, n. 582.

mafia method)^[54].

Following the approach of case law, the aggravating circumstance in question applies both to members of the mafia association and to non-members.

6.2. Concurrence of mitigating and aggravating circumstances

Paragraph 2 considers the possible combination of heterogeneous circumstances.

Specifically, mitigating circumstances - other than those referred to in Article 98^[55] of the Criminal Code and Article 114^[56] of the Criminal Code— cannot be considered equivalent or prevalent on aggravating circumstance of the mafia method or mafia facilitation: that is, reductions of the sanction should be made on the amount of the penalty resulting after the increase deriving from the application of the aggravating circumstance^[57].

Furthermore, pursuant to paragraph 3, there is a mitigating circumstance in relation to cases where the person under investigation or charged with crimes under Article 416-bis or with aggravated crimes under the provision in question, by dissociating himself from the criminal framework, take steps to prevent the criminal activity from having further consequences, including the cooperation with the judicial police authorities in order to allow them to gather decisive evidence for the reconstruction of the facts or for the identification or arrest of the perpetrators of the crimes^[58].

Paragraph 4 specifies that, in the case of active dissociation referred to in paragraph 3^[59], neither the aggravating circumstance provided for in paragraph 1 nor the rules established in paragraph 2 for the case of concurrence of heterogeneous circumstances, shall apply.

Moreover, according to the last paragraph (inserted by Act no. 60 of 2023), crimes aggravated by the circumstances just mentioned are always prosecuted *ex officio*.

[54] Cass. pen., sez. VI, 31 gennaio 2023, n. 11352 in which “The aggravating circumstance of aiding and abetting the mafia, provided for in Article 416-bis.1 of the Criminal Code, postulating that the crime is committed for the specific purpose of facilitating the activities of a mafia association, necessarily implies proof of the actual and not merely supposed existence of such an association”. Also see, Cass. pen., sez. III, 28 gennaio 2021, n. 23335, in which “The aggravating circumstance referred to in Article 416-bis.1 of the Criminal Code applies, in the form of mafia facilitation, when the continuous payment of money to such a group by an entrepreneur is aimed at obtaining “protection” and support in the acquisition of economic contracts”. It is worth noting, having recently intervened to settle the dispute over the nature of the aggravating circumstance in terms of facilitating the association, that it is subjective at the factual level, relating to the motives for committing the crime (Cass. pen., SS.UU., 19 dicembre 2019, n. 8545).

[55] Mitigating circumstance of under the age of eighteen.

[56] Mitigating circumstances. If the judge considers that the contribution made by any of the persons who participated in the crime pursuant to Articles 110 and 113 was of minimal importance in the preparation or execution of the crime, the penalty may be reduced. This provision does not apply in the cases referred to in Article 112. The penalty may also be reduced for those who were persuaded to commit the offense or to cooperate in the offense, when the conditions set out in paragraphs 3 and 4 of the first paragraph and in the third paragraph of Article 112 are met.

[57] Cass. pen., sez. II, 17 dicembre 2021, n. 9526 in which “In the event of multiple aggravating circumstances with special effect, the aggravating circumstance referred to in Article 416-bis.1 of the Criminal Code must be excluded from the balancing assessment, since, for the purposes of calculating the applicable increases in penalty, the general rule provided for in Article 63, paragraph 4, of the Criminal Code does not apply to it, but rather the autonomous derogatory provision referred to in the aforementioned Article 416-bis.1 of the Criminal Code, which provides for an increase in the penalty from one third to one half”.

[58] Cass. pen., sez. V, 22 marzo 2022, n. 18438, in which “The confession may justify the granting of the special mitigating circumstance referred to in Article 416-bis.1, paragraph 3, of the Criminal Code, provided that the judge favorably assesses the truthfulness, genuineness, and reliability of the narrative, giving logical reasons for any confirming evidence acquired and the reasons why the suspicion of self-slander should be excluded”.

[59] The judge's examination of the existence of the conditions for the special mitigating circumstance of dissociation, provided for organized crime offenses by Article 8 of Decree Law No. 152 of May 13, 1991, converted with amendments by Act No. 203 of July 12, 1991 (and now by Article 416-bis.1, paragraph 3, of the Criminal Code), can only be limited to what the defendant has stated in the individual proceedings concerning the crimes that are the subject of those proceedings, only in relation to which the decisiveness and concreteness of the contribution provided are relevant, with the contribution made in other proceedings for different criminal matters remaining outside the scope of that examination. (Cass. pen., sez. II, 15 ottobre 2021, n. 46385).

Conclusions

The analysis of Article 416-bis of the Italian Criminal Code confirms the extraordinary complexity and adaptability of the mafia-type association offence. The evolution of case law demonstrates how the ‘mafia method’ has progressively expanded beyond its historical sociological roots, allowing courts to address both traditional criminal structures and their relocated or emerging counterparts. The jurisprudence on external participation further highlights the need for a nuanced assessment of contributory conduct, capable of capturing forms of support that, while external to the associative bond, strengthen its operational capacity. Likewise, the interpretation of aggravating circumstances underscores the central role of intimidation as an objective and functional element within the offence. Overall, the dynamic nature of Article 416-bis reveals a legal instrument that continues to evolve in response to new manifestations of organised crime, balancing guarantees with the imperative of protecting public order, democratic institutions, and economic legality.

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